

To Study the Structural Parameters and Surface Curvature of Fullerenes

A
DISSERTATION

Submitted By

MANDEEP SINGH

2106103003

In Partial Fulfillment of Requirements for the Degree of

MASTER OF SCIENCE
IN
PHYSICS

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS
UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF SCIENCES
RAYAT BAHRA UNIVERSITY, MOHALI

140401

June, 2023

CANDIDATE'S DECLARATION

I hereby certify that the work which is being presented in the dissertation, en-titled "TO STUDY THE STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS AND SURFACE CURVATURE OF FULLERENES" in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Science in Physics and submitted in University, is my own work carried out during a period of 4th Semester under supervision of Dr. Deepak Agnihotri.

Mandeep Singh
2106103003

This is to certify that the above statement made by the candidate is correct to the best of my knowledge.

Dr. Deepak Agnihotri
Deptt. of Physics

The Dissertation Viva-Voice examination of Mandeep Sigh has been held on

Signature of Supervisor

Signature of External Examiner

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project work is the end of my journey in obtaining my Master's degree. This dissertation has been kept on track and been seen through to completion with the support and encouragement of numerous people including my professors, my well wishers and my classmates.

First and foremost I would like to thank God Almighty for giving me strength, knowledge, ability and opportunity to undertake this project work and complete it satisfactorily.

I would like to express my deep gratitude to Dr. Manoj Bali (DEAN) and Dr. M.S.Mehta (H.O.D.) at USS (RAYAT BAHRA UNIVERSITY, MOHALI) for their constant motivation and encouragement at the times I needed it the most.

I take pride in acknowledging the insightful guidance of Dr. Deepak Agnihotri (ASSISTANT PROFESSOR), for sparing his valuable time and providing his heartfelt support and guidance whenever I approached him.

I would also like to extend my thanks to University School of Sciences (RAYAT BAHRA UNIVERSITY) for providing the computational support in computer lab. Finally, I would like to thank my parents for their support and encouragement throughout the study.

Date:.....

MANDEEP SINGH

ABSTRACT

This work reports the structure of different fullerenes such as C₂₈, C₃₂, C₃₆, C₄₀, C₄₄, C₅₀ and C₆₀ of variable size. We have studied the structural properties such as average diameter, C-C bond length and C=C bond length and surface curvature in all the fullerenes considered. The average diameter of fullerenes may vary from 4.89 Å to 7.15 Å. The values of average diameter for fullerene C₂₈, C₃₂, C₃₆, C₄₀, C₄₄, C₅₀, C₆₀ is found to be 4.89 Å, 5.19 Å, 5.52 Å, 6.05 Å, 6.64 Å, 7.50 Å and 7.15 Å respectively. This is clear that as the size of fullerenes increases, their average diameter also increases, with C₂₈ having the minimum value and C₆₀ having the maximum value. The C-C bond length varies from 1.50-1.53 Å for C₂₈, 1.46-1.51 Å for C₃₂, 1.46-1.50 Å for C₃₆, 1.45-1.48 Å for C₄₀, 1.46-1.50 Å for C₄₄, 1.46-1.49 Å for C₅₀, 1.46 Å for C₆₀, while the C=C bond length varies from 1.41-1.47 Å for C₂₈, 1.40-1.45 Å for C₃₂, 1.42-1.45 Å for C₃₆, 1.41-1.44 Å for C₄₀, 1.41-1.45 Å for C₄₄, 1.42-1.45 Å for C₅₀ and 1.41 Å for C₆₀. C=C bond length is found to be smaller than C-C bond length in all the fullerenes considered. We have calculated the pyramidalization angle in fullerenes at different sites on the surface. A new solution method was developed to perform vector analysis of the pi-orbital axis. The equations for solving the pyramidalization angle were obtained based on the circular cone model. This model requires the atomic coordinates of the conjugated central atom and the three attached atoms. Systematic calculation of mean diameter, C-C and C=C bond length of fullerenes were measured using the Vesta. Moreover, systematic calculations of the pyramidalization angle of fullerenes were performed using the method we developed. The relationship of pyramidalization angle and reactivity for fullerenes was also discussed. As the size of fullerenes increases, their pyramidalization angle and surface curvature decreases, with C₂₈ having the maximum value and C₆₀ having the minimum value.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER NO.	PAGE NO.
ABSTRACT	
LIST OF TABLES	
LIST OF FIGURES	
LIST OF SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS	
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Fullerenes	1
1.2 History	2
1.3 Structure of C ₆₀	2
1.4 Symmetry of C ₆₀	3
1.5 Types of fullerenes	4
1.6 Isolated pentagon rule (IPR)	6
1.7 Surface curvature of fullerenes	06-07
2. LITERATURE REVIEW	08-10
3. METHODOLOGY	11-15
4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	16-17
4.1 Average diameter	18-32
4.2 Bond length	33-44
4.3 Surface curvature	45-57
5. CONCLUSION AND SCOPE OF WORK	58-60
6. REFERENCES	61-64

LIST OF TABLES

S.NO.	NAME	PAGE
1.	Pair of carbon atoms considered to measure the diameter of C ₂₈	20
2.	Pair of carbon atoms considered to measure the diameter of C ₃₂	22
3.	Pair of carbon atoms considered to measure the diameter of C ₃₆	24
4.	Pair of carbon atoms considered to measure the diameter of C ₄₀	26
5.	Pair of carbon atoms considered to measure the diameter of C ₄₄	28
6.	Pair of carbon atoms considered to measure the diameter of C ₅₀	30
7.	Pair of carbon atoms considered to measure the diameter of C ₆₀	32
8.	Bond length measurement for fullerene C ₂₈	34
9.	Bond length measurement for fullerene C ₃₂	35
10.	Bond length measurement for fullerene C ₃₆	37
11.	Bond length measurement for fullerene C ₄₀	38
12.	Bond length measurement for fullerene C ₄₄	40
13.	Bond length measurement for fullerene C ₅₀	41
14.	Bond length measurement for fullerene C ₆₀	43
15.	Diameters and bond lengths of fullerenes	44
16.	Pyramidalization angle measurement for fullerenes	56-57

LIST OF FIGURES

S.NO.	NAME	PAGE
1.	Allotropes of Carbon	1
2.	Structure of fullerene C ₆₀	2
3.	Rotation symmetries of fullerene C ₆₀	3
4.	Types of fullerenes	5-6
5.	POAV Angle	11
6.	A circular cone method of POAV	12
7.	Ground state structures of fullerenes	16-17
8.	Diameter of fullerene C ₂₈	18-19
9.	Diameter of fullerene C ₃₂	20-21
10.	Diameter of fullerene C ₃₆	22-23
11.	Diameter of fullerene C ₄₀	24-25
12.	Diameter of fullerene C ₄₄	26-27
13.	Diameter of fullerene C ₅₀	28-29
14.	Diameter of fullerene C ₆₀	30-31
15.	Structure of fullerene C ₂₈ showing bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms	33
16.	Structure of fullerene C ₃₂ showing bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms	34-35
17.	Structure of fullerene C ₃₆ showing bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms	36
18.	Structure of fullerene C ₄₀ showing bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms	37-38
19.	Structure of fullerene C ₄₄ showing bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms	39
20.	Structure of fullerene C ₅₀ showing bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms	40-41
21.	Structure of fullerene C ₆₀ showing bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms	42
22.	Average diameter of fullerenes	44

23. Structure of fullerene C ₂₈ showing pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms	45-46
24. Structure of fullerene C ₃₂ showing pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms	47-48
25. Structure of fullerene C ₃₆ showing pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms	48-49
26. Structure of fullerene C ₄₀ showing pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms	50-51
27. Structure of fullerene C ₄₄ showing pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms	51-52
28. Structure of fullerene C ₅₀ showing pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms	53-54
29. Structure of fullerene C ₆₀ showing pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms	54-55

LIST OF SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS

S.NO	SYMBOL	MEANING
1.	2D	2 Dimensional
2.	3D	3 Dimensional
3.	IPR	Isolated pentagon rule
4.	TEM	Transmission electron microscopy
5.	DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
6.	IMEC	Interuniversitair micro-electronica centrum
7.	NRAM	Nano-Ram

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. FULLERENES

There are many allotropes of carbon like graphite, diamond, coal etc as shown in fig 1. Fullerenes are the third allotropic form of carbon composed entirely of carbon and exist in the form of a hollow sphere, ellipsoid or tube. Fullerenes having spherical shape are called Buckyballs [1] where as cylindrical shaped fullerenes are called Carbon Nanotubes as shown in fig 2. This allotrope has truncated icosahedrons [2] structure. Fullerenes are a group of closed-cage carbon molecule denoted by their empirical formula C_n , where n is the no of carbon atoms. First fullerene to be discovered was C_{60} which is called Buckminster fullerene. It derives its name from the geodesic dome designed by an architect Richard Buckminster fuller whose shape it resembles. Fullerenes have similar structure like graphite except they may also have pentagonal [3] rings in their structures that prevent the sheet from being planar like graphite.

Figure 1: Allotropes of carbon a) diamond b) graphite c) Lonsdaleite d) C_{60} e) C_{540} f) C_{70} g) Amorphous carbon h) carbon nanotube

1.2. HISTORY

The existence of fullerenes was first predicted by Eiji Osawa of Toyohashi University of Technology in 1970 who theoretically discussed the possibility of polyhedral carbon clusters and their properties. It was then in 1985 that they were experimentally discovered by Harold W Kroto, Robert F Curl and Richard E Smalley at Rice University who discovered fullerenes in the sooty residue created by vaporizing carbon in a helium atmosphere. In the mass spectrum of the product, discrete peaks were observed corresponding to masses 720 and 840. They suggested that these peaks corresponds to C_{60} and C_{70} . They won the Nobel Prize for chemistry in 1996 for their phenomenal discovery after which fullerene family was discovered.

1.3. STRUCTURE OF C_{60}

These have interconnected carbon atoms in 20 hexagonal and 12 pentagonal rings. The shape is the same as that of a soccer ball [4]. Imagine the black portions are pentagons [5] and white are hexagons and we put carbon atoms at all these 60 points, then the structure obtained is that of Buckminster fullerene. In C_{60} , each carbon atom is covalently bonded to three neighboring atoms is sp^2 hybridized [6]. The C_{60} molecule has two bond lengths, the $C=C$ can be considered double bonds and are shorter than $C-C$ which are single bonds. C_{60} is not superaromatic as it tends to avoid double bonds in pentagonal rings, resulting in poor electron delocalization. As a result C_{60} behaves like electron deficient alkenes and react readily with electron rich species.

Figure 2: Structure of C_{60}

1.4 SYMMETRY OF C_{60} MOLECULE

C_{60} , being highly symmetric [7], one can observe many symmetric operations of a molecule such as rotations [8] around the axis, reflections in a plane and inversions also. Since all the symmetric operations result in an equivalent structure, most of them go through the centre of mass of the molecule. For C_{60} , there are three kinds of rotation axis as shown in fig 3. The most common is the 5-fold axis which operates at the centre of two facing pentagons becoming the highest symmetry axis. Next is the 3-fold axis which passes through the centre of two facing hexagons. At last there is 2-fold axis which passes through the centre of edges between two hexagons. Since there are 12 pentagons, so there are six 5-fold axes, likewise for 20 hexagons, there are 10 different 3-fold axes. Since each hexagon is neighbored by three hexagons, there are 30 edges thus forming 15 different 2-fold axes. In total C_{60} molecule has 120 different symmetry operations contributing to the title of most symmetric molecule synthesized.

Figure 3: Rotation symmetries of C_{60}

1.5. TYPES OF FULLERENES

On the basis of structural variations, following types of fullerenes are there :

NANOTUBES

These consist of two dimensional hexagonal lattice of carbon atoms have very small dimensions. These are hollow from inside like a tube with single or multiple boundaries as shown in fig 4(a). Nanotubes [9] are used mostly in electronic industries, space technology and in paper batteries.

BUCKYBALL CLUSTERS

C_{20} is its finest and the smallest fullerene that occurs in nature with no two pentagons sharing an edge. The most common buckyball cluster [10] is C_{60} as shown in fig 4(b). It can be found in soot or coal.

MEGATUBES

As the name suggests mega which means large, these have larger diameter as compared to nanotubes. Megatubes [11] have walls of different sizes.

POLYMERS

These are macromolecules attached by covalent bonds formed under high temperature and pressure. Polymers [12] comprises of carbon chains. These chains can be 2D or 3D as shown in fig 4(c).

NANO-ONIONS

These are spherical in shape they have multiple carbon layered structures with a Buckyball core as shown in fig 4(d). Nano onions [13] are used as good lubricants.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 4: Types of fullerenes a) carbon nanotubes b) Buckyball clusters c) polymers d) nano onions.

1.6. ISOLATED PENTAGON RULE (IPR) IN FULLERENES

After the discovery of fullerenes, Kroto [14] in 1987 proposed IPR [15] rule which states that the most stable fullerenes are those in which no two pentagons share an edge i.e each pentagon is completely surrounded by hexagons, which results in the stability of fullerenes. C_{60} is the first stable fullerene because it is the smallest one to obey this rule. The IPR can be justified from local strain in geometry and Π –electronic resonance energy of fullerenes in which a Π bond shared by two pentagons has a large negative bond resonance energy, resulting in increase in kinetic instability. The existence of such highly anti-aromatic structures distinguishes IPR violating fullerenes from isolated pentagon isomers.

1.7 SURFACE CURVATURE OF FULLERENES

Fullerenes are form of nanocarbon with curved π -conjugations, have aroused considerable attention due to the fascinating structural, electronic and mechanic properties[16-23]. Fullerenes are usually convex carbon cages comprising several hexagons and exactly 12 pentagons, while CNTs only contain the hexagons. It is known that the families of the carbon cages and tubes are composed of various isomers and structures. Thus the POAV method provides a wonderful description for fullerenes because the nonplanar π -conjugations within hybrid hexagon-pentagon carbon-based networks can be related to the stability and the chemical reactivity[17,18,21-25]. Several literatures[26,27,28] have paid attention to the solution of POAV equations for the conjugated carbon atoms. However, the previous solutions still have some limitations to obtain

the information about the pyramidalization angle and orbital rehybridization of the conjugation atom. The obtained equations[27-28] require the values of the three angles made by the σ -bonds at the central atom, but it would be more commonly to use the atomic coordinates of the conjugated atom and its three attached atoms. It should be pointed out that the previous methods could also use the atomic coordinates to obtain the pyramidalization angles, but it needs that the coordinate system must be defined such that the central atom is located at the origin, the first attached atom lies along the x direction, the second atom in the x, y plane, and the third atom out of the x, y plane. These facts expose the flaws of the previous methods. Thus developing new model and method to easily perform the POAV analysis is still necessary. Furthermore, systematic studies on the POAV of fullerenes with different sizes have not been reported up until now and only the pyramidalization angles of several structures were given[29, 17, 18, 21-27,30,31] according to the best of our knowledge.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past two decades, many different models have been presented to explain the formation of fullerenes from graphite, these mechanisms can be divided into four major groups :- i) The pentagon road [32,33], ii) The fullerene road [34], iii) Ring coalescence [35,36], iv) Shrinking hot giant model [37,38]. All these are bottom up techniques [39, 40]. In 2010 Andrey chivilin, Ute Kaiser, Elena Bichoutskaia and Andrei N.Khlobystov explained Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [41] technique to obtain a perfect fullerene molecule, which is a top down mechanism and includes four critical steps: i) loss of carbon atoms at the edge of graphene, leading to ii) the formation of pentagons, which iii) triggers the curving of graphene into a bowl shaped structure which iv) subsequently zips up its open edges to form a closed fullerene structure.

The experimental and theoretical study of carbon clusters has remained a topic with a long history. Much information about the exciting and recent developments about C_{60} and other fullerenes are covered in various recent research reviews. Erik S. Soensen, Catherine Kallin, A John Berlinsky of MC Master University in 2009, studied the properties of the smallest member of fullerene family, C_{20} . It is a molecule with dodecahedral cage structure. In light of the isolated pentagon rule (IPR) which states that fullerenes with isolated pentagons are kinetically much more stable than their fused pentagon counterparts i.e the most stable fullerene should have 12 pentagons as far apart as possible, showing that C_{20} is highly unstable and thus referred to as unconventional fullerene [42].

Moving forward the relative stabilities of closed fullerenes as well as cohesive energies for clusters $n=18, 20, 22, 24, 26, 28, 30, 32, 36, 50$ and 60 were studied by Martin Feyereisen, Maciej Gutowski and Jack Simons in 1991 using ab initio self consistent field and 2nd order Moller Plesset perturbation theory. For $n \geq 32$, fullerenes are found to be most stable and their cohesive energies are found to increase monotonically as n varies from 26 to 60. Hence it is possible that the smallest cluster for which fullerene structure is most stable has $n < 32$.

The π -electrons and the orbital rehybridization are of great significance for the nonplanar conjugated molecules[29,44-45]. On the basis of the fact, the pi-orbital axis vector (POAV) analysis[26,46] was usually performed to predict and study the relative stability and the chemical reactivity of the aromatic systems with distortion[26,46-49]. According to the POAV theory, the pi-orbital axis vector is defined as the vector which makes the three equal angles ($\theta_{\sigma\pi}$) the three σ -bonds at the central atom with three coordinated atoms, as shown in Fig.5. Then the pyramidalization angle θ_P is defined as $\theta_P = (\theta_{\sigma\pi} - 90)^\circ$. It has been shown that, with a single assumption, it is possible to obtain analytical solutions for the rehybridization in such compounds, which in turn leads directly to the orientation of the pi-orbital axis vectors and hence to a measure of pi-orbital alignment and overlap in the distorted π -electron systems of known geometry. The POAV analysis could provide a vivid picture of the π -bonding for nonplanar conjugated systems and the manner in which the σ -system has rehybridized and adjusted to facilitate the maintenance of favorable pi-orbital overlap. The method is nonparametric and only requires geometrical parameters of the molecule or molecular fragment for its implementation. Thus the POAV theory has been successfully applied to discuss the structure-property relationship for the conjugated systems with nonplanar structure[26,46-49]. Fullerenes are form of nanocarbon with curved π -conjugations, have aroused considerable attention due to the fascinating structural, electronic and mechanic properties[16-23]. Fullerenes are usually convex carbon cages comprising several hexagons and exactly 12 pentagons, while CNTs only contain the hexagons. It is known that the families of the carbon cages and tubes are composed of various isomers and structures. Thus the POAV method provides a wonderful description for fullerenes because the nonplanar π -conjugations within hybrid hexagon-pentagon carbon-based networks can be related to the stability and the chemical reactivity[17,18,21-25]. Several literatures[26,27,28] have paid attention to the solution of POAV equations for the conjugated carbon atoms. However, the previous solutions still have some limitations to obtain the information about the pyramidalization angle and orbital rehybridization of the conjugation atom. The obtained equations[27-28] require the values of the three angles made by the σ -bonds at the central atom, but it would be more commonly to use the atomic coordinates of the conjugated atom and its three attached atoms. It should be pointed out that the previous methods could also use the atomic coordinates to obtain the pyramidalization angles, but it needs that the coordinate system must be defined such that the central atom is located at the origin, the first attached atom lies along the x direction, the second atom in the x, y plane, and the third atom out of the x, y plane.

These facts expose the flaws of the previous methods. Thus developing new model and method to easily perform the POAV analysis is still necessary. Furthermore, systematic studies on the POAV of fullerenes with different sizes have not been reported up until now and only the pyramidalization angles of several structures were given[29, 17, 18, 21-27,30,31] according to the best of our knowledge.

In this paper, we have built a new model to calculate the POAV. Then the solution of the pyramidalization angles was obtained based on the model we proposed. The solution of POAV in this paper merely requires the atomic coordinates of the central atom and its three attached atoms, and removes the limitation of coordinate system. Moreover, a systematic calculation on the pyramidalization angles of various fullerenes and CNTs was performed using the equations we obtained, and the relationship of the pyramidalization angle and the stability for the carbon cages and tubes was also discussed. We hope our studies would cause further attention of the POAV theory and its applications in fullerenes.

CHAPTER 3 METHODOLOGY

Visualization for electronic and structural analysis (VESTA) is a 3-D visualization program for structural models, volumetric data such as electronic, nuclear densities and crystal morphologies. This tool has been used to study the ground state structural properties of various fullerenes. The input atomic coordinate file of different fullerenes are incorporated in VESTA so as to generate the geometrical ground state structures of fullerenes. With the help of VESTA, the carbon atoms involved for measuring the average diameter and C-C and C=C bond length have been numbered systematically in all the fullerenes considered and corresponding results are obtained after measurements. VESTA has also been used to find the surface curvature in various ground state structures of fullerenes. Model of the Circular cone satisfies the pi-orbital angular vector (POAV).

Figure 5: POAV angle

We construct a circular cone with a conical axis PO and the vertex angle, where O is the vertex of the cone. The central atom is located at the vertex (O) of the circular cone, and the three attached atoms are the arbitrary three points (A, B and C) on the conical surface.

$$\Theta_{\sigma\pi} = \text{POA} = \text{POB} = \text{POC} = (180 - \Theta)^\circ \quad (\text{i})$$

If we obtain the vertex angle Θ of the circular cone, then we can get the value of $\Theta_{\sigma\pi}$ using the following equations and then pyramidalization angle obtained by:

$$\Theta_p = (\Theta_{\sigma\pi} - 90)^\circ = (180 - \Theta - 90)^\circ = (90 - \Theta)^\circ \quad (\text{ii})$$

For solving the POAV equations we require the coordinates of the conjugated atom $O(x_o, y_o, z_o)$ and other three attached atoms $A(x_a, y_a, z_a)$, $B(x_b, y_b, z_b)$, $C(x_c, y_c, z_c)$

As, the line PO in the space analytic geometry then the space in line is:

$$x - x_s/l = y - y_s/m = z - z_s/n \quad (\text{iii})$$

Here, $l = x_o - x_s$, $m = y_o - y_s$, $n = z_o - z_s$

$$[l(x - x_o) + m(y - y_o) + n(z - z_o)]^2 = [(x - x_o)^2 + (y - y_o)^2 + (z - z_o)^2](l^2 + m^2 + n^2)\cos^2\theta \quad (\text{iv})$$

Figure 6: A circular cone model of POAV

The points of A, B and C are the arbitrary three points on the conical surface, thus the coordinates of A, B and C satisfy the equation of the circular cone. Insert the coordinates of the three atoms into equation (iv), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
[l(x_a-x_0) + m(y_a-y_0)+n(z_a-z_0)]^2 &= [(x_a-x_0)^2+(y_a-y_0)^2+(z_a-z_0)^2](l^2+m^2+n^2)\cos^2\theta \\
[l(x_b-x_0) + m(y_b-y_0)+n(z_b-z_0)]^2 &= [(x_b-x_0)^2+(y_b-y_0)^2+(z_b-z_0)^2](l^2+m^2+n^2)\cos^2\theta \\
[l(x_c-x_0) + m(y_c-y_0)+n(z_c-z_0)]^2 &= [(x_c-x_0)^2+(y_c-y_0)^2+(z_c-z_0)^2](l^2+m^2+n^2)\cos^2\theta
\end{aligned} \tag{v}$$

In equation (v) $(x_i-x_0)^2+ (y_i-y_0)^2+ (z_i-z_0)^2$, with $i= a,b$ and c , is equal to the square of the distances of the corresponding line segments OA, OB and OC respectively, and thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
|OA| &= \sqrt{(x_a-x_0)^2+(y_a-y_0)^2+(z_a-z_0)^2} \\
|OB| &= \sqrt{(x_b-x_0)^2+(y_b-y_0)^2+(z_b-z_0)^2} \\
|OC| &= \sqrt{(x_c-x_0)^2+(y_c-y_0)^2+(z_c-z_0)^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{vi}$$

$$l^2+m^2+n^2=(x_0-x_s)^2+(y_0-y_s)^2+(z_0-z_s)^2= |PO|^2 \tag{vii}$$

Similarly $l^2+m^2+n^2$ is the square of the distance of PO and thus as, the position of point P at the line PO is arbitrary and unrelated to the POAV results, for the convenience we assume that

$$|PO|^2=l^2+m^2+n^2=1 \tag{viii}$$

Based on equations (vii) and (viii) ; then equation (v) then can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
[l(x_a-x_0)+m(y_a-y_0)+n(z_a-z_0)]^2 &= |OA|^2 \cos^2\theta \\
[l(x_b-x_0)+m(y_b-y_0)+n(z_b-z_0)]^2 &= |OB|^2 \cos^2\theta \\
[l(x_c-x_0)+m(y_c-y_0)+n(z_c-z_0)]^2 &= |OC|^2 \cos^2\theta
\end{aligned} \tag{ix}$$

Here above, the angle θ of the circular cone is an acute angle now, from equation (ix) we can obtain :

$$\begin{aligned}
l(x_a-x_0)+m(y_a-y_0)+n(z_a-z_0) &= |OA| \cos\theta \\
l(x_b-x_0)+m(y_b-y_0)+n(z_b-z_0) &= |OA| \cos\theta \\
l(x_c-x_0)+m(y_c-y_0)+n(z_c-z_0) &= |OA| \cos\theta
\end{aligned} \tag{x}$$

Taking two equations randomly from the above equation (x) and dividing each other, by this we get a new linear equation system:

$$\begin{aligned}
[|OB|(x_a-x_0)-|OA|(x_b-x_0)]l+ [|OB|(y_a-y_0)-|OA|(y_b-y_0)]m+ [|OB|(z_a-z_0)-|OA|(z_b-z_0)]n &= 0 \\
[|OC|(x_a-x_0)-|OA|(x_c-x_0)]l+ [|OC|(y_a-y_0)-|OA|(y_c-y_0)]m+ [|OC|(z_a-z_0)-|OA|(z_c-z_0)]n &= 0 \\
[|OC|(x_b-x_0)-|OB|(x_c-x_0)]l+ [|OC|(y_b-y_0)-|OB|(y_c-y_0)]m+ [|OC|(z_b-z_0)-|OB|(z_c-z_0)]n &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{xi}$$

In short , the equation (xi) is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_1l + a_2m + a_3n &= 0 \\ b_1l + b_2m + b_3n &= 0 \\ c_1l + c_2m + c_3n &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{xii})$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o), a_2 = |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o), a_3 = |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o) \\ b_1 &= |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o), b_2 = |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o), b_3 = |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o) \\ c_1 &= |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o), c_2 = |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o), c_3 = |\text{OB}|(x_a - x_o) - |\text{OA}|(x_b - x_o) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{xiii})$$

by solving the equation (xii) the solution is given by :

$$\begin{aligned} l &= a_2b_3 - a_3b_2 / \sqrt{(a_2b_3 - a_3b_2)^2 + (a_3b_1 - a_1b_3)^2 + (a_1b_2 - a_2b_1)^2} \\ m &= a_3b_1 - a_1b_3 / \sqrt{(a_2b_3 - a_3b_2)^2 + (a_3b_1 - a_1b_3)^2 + (a_1b_2 - a_2b_1)^2} \\ n &= a_1b_2 - a_2b_1 / \sqrt{(a_2b_3 - a_3b_2)^2 + (a_3b_1 - a_1b_3)^2 + (a_1b_2 - a_2b_1)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{xiv})$$

In equation (xiii) a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2 and b_3 are constants, and from that values can be obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= \sqrt{((x_b - x_o)^2 + (y_b - y_o)^2 + (z_b - z_o)^2)}(x_a - x_o) - \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)}(x_b - x_o) \\ a_2 &= \sqrt{((x_b - x_o)^2 + (y_b - y_o)^2 + (z_b - z_o)^2)}(y_a - x_o) - \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)}(y_b - x_o) \\ a_3 &= \sqrt{((x_b - x_o)^2 + (y_b - y_o)^2 + (z_b - z_o)^2)}(z_a - x_o) - \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)}(z_b - x_o) \\ b_1 &= \sqrt{((x_c - x_o)^2 + (y_c - y_o)^2 + (z_c - z_o)^2)}(x_a - x_o) - \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)}(x_c - x_o) \\ b_2 &= \sqrt{((x_c - x_o)^2 + (y_c - y_o)^2 + (z_c - z_o)^2)}(y_a - x_o) - \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)}(y_c - x_o) \\ b_3 &= \sqrt{((x_c - x_o)^2 + (y_c - y_o)^2 + (z_c - z_o)^2)}(z_a - x_o) - \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)}(z_c - x_o) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{xv})$$

As , the vertex angle Θ of the circular cone is an acute angle then , according to equation (x) the equation (xvi) is written as,

$$\begin{aligned} \cos\Theta &= |l(x_a - x_o) + m(y_a - y_o) + n(z_a - z_o)| / |\text{OA}| \\ \cos\Theta &= |l(x_a - x_o) + m(y_a - y_o) + n(z_a - z_o)| / \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{xvi})$$

The values of l, m and n can be calculated by knowing the coordinates of the central atom and then by knowing the values of $l, m,$ and n we can obtain the value of the vertex angle (Θ)

$$\Theta = \cos^{-1} (|l(x_a - x_o) + m(y_a - y_o) + n(z_a - z_o)| / \sqrt{((x_a - x_o)^2 + (y_a - y_o)^2 + (z_a - z_o)^2)}) \quad (\text{xvii})$$

Thus , the angle can be obtained by using equation (xvii) And, according to equation (i)

$$\Theta_{\sigma\pi} = (180-\Theta)^{\circ} \quad (\text{xviii})$$

And the pyramidalization angle Θ_p can also be obtained by equation (ii)

$$\Theta_p = (90-\Theta)^{\circ} \quad (\text{xix})$$

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The ground state structures of fullerenes were generated using their xyz files in vesta, Their raster images were taken as shown in fig 5a, 5b, 5c, 5d, 5e, 5f. Ground state structure of C_{28} contains 28 carbon atoms, C_{32} contains 32 carbon atoms, C_{36} contains 36 carbon atoms, C_{40} contains 40 carbon atoms, C_{50} contains 50 carbon atoms and C_{60} contains 60 carbon atoms.

a)

b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 5: Ground state structures of fullerenes a) C₂₈, b) C₃₂, c) C₃₆, d) C₄₀, e) C₄₄, f) C₅₀, g) C₆₀

4.1 AVERAGE DIAMETER

The average diameter of fullerenes have been calculated using distance formula $[(x_1-x_2)^2 + (y_1-y_2)^2 + (z_1-z_2)^2]^{1/2}$. After generating the fullerene structures in VESTA, extreme atoms of a fullerene structure were considered systematically and by substituting the atomic coordinates, different diameters corresponding to different pair of extreme carbon atoms were calculated. Finally the average diameters for different fullerenes have been calculated. The structure of C₂₈ showing various possibilities for measuring diameters is shown in fig 6. Pair of carbon atoms chosen to find the diameter of C₂₈ is shown in Fig 6(a) C₁₀ and C₁₉, the co-ordinates of C₁₀ and C₁₉ are (2.648, 0.292, -0.675) and (-2.648, 0.292, 0.675) respectively, the mentioned coordinates were substituted in distance formula so as to get the diameter of 5.47Å. Similarly, fig 6(b), 6(c), 6(d), 6(e) and 6(f) shows the pair of carbon atoms chosen to measure the diameter C₄-C₁₆, C₂-C₂₇, C₉-C₂₈, C₁-C₂₃ and C₁₅-C₂₄ respectively. The calculated values of diameters are mentioned in table 1 and the average diameter calculated is 4.90Å.

Figure 6: Different orientations of C₂₈ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of diameter a) C₁₉-C₁₀, b) C₄-C₁₆, c) C₉-C₂₈, d) C₁-C₂₃, e) C₂-C₂₇, f) C₁₅-C₂₄ .

Table 1. Diameters of C₂₈ corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen.

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)
1	C ₂ -C ₂₇	4.76	6	C ₈ -C ₁₈	5.57
2	C ₄ -C ₁₆	4.41	7	C ₆ -C ₁₇	4.29
3	C ₁₀ -C ₁₉	5.46	8	C ₁₄ -C ₂₆	4.76
4	C ₁ -C ₂₃	5.06	9	C ₇ -C ₁₂	5.06
5	C ₉ -C ₂₈	5.06	10	C ₁₅ -C ₂₄	4.57

The same procedure has been repeated to find the average diameter of C₃₂, Fig 7(a) shows two extreme carbon atoms C₅ and C₇ chosen to measure the diameter. The coordinates of C₅ and C₇ are (-0.329, -1.325, 2.385) and (-0.329, 1.325, -2.385), these coordinates were substituted in distance formula so as to obtain the diameter of 5.46Å. Similarly fig. 7(b),7(c),7(d),7(d),7(e) shows the pair of carbon atoms chosen to measure the diameter respectively. The calculated values of diameters are mentioned in Table 2 and the average diameter is 5.19Å.

Figure 7: Different orientations of C₃₂ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of diameter a) C₅-C₇, b) C₂₄-C₃₁, c) C₁-C₂, d) C₂₂-C₂₇; e) C₂₁-C₃₂.

Table 2. Diameters of C₃₂ corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen.

S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)	S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)
1	C ₄ -C ₆	5.46	6	C ₁₉ -C ₁₇	5.20
2	C ₅ -C ₇	5.45	7	C ₁₆ -C ₁₈	5.20
3	C ₂₁ -C ₃₂	4.81	8	C ₃ -C ₁₂	5.33
4	C ₂₄ -C ₃₁	4.92	9	C ₂₃ -C ₂₈	4.92
5	C ₁ -C ₂	5.69	10	C ₂₂ -C ₂₇	4.92

The diameter corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen is C₂₃ and C₃₃ shown in figure 8(a). The coordinates of C₂₃ and C₃₃ are (-1.433, 1.162, -2.013) and (1.433, -1.162, 2.013) which were substituted in distance formula in order to obtain the diameter of 5.46Å, similarly fig 8(b), 8(c), 8(d), 8(e) shows pair of carbon atoms C₁₃-C₂₂, C₁₄-C₁₆, C₇-C₃₈ and C₄-C₇ respectively. The calculated values of diameters are mentioned in Table 3 and the average diameter is 5.52Å.

a)

b)

Figure 8: Different orientations of C₃₆ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of diameter a) C₂₃-C₃₃, b) C₁₃-C₂₂, c) C₁₄-C₁₆, d) C₇-C₃₈, e) C₄-C₇.

Table 3: Diameters of C₃₆ corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen.

S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter in Å	S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter in Å
1	C4-C17	5.20	6	C5-C29	5.99
2	C7-C36	5.99	7	C11-C19	5.21
3	C14-C16	5.46	8	C25-C31	5.21
4	C22-C13	5.46	9	C10-C28	5.99
5	C23-C33	5.46	10	C12-C21	5.21

Figure 9 Represents various orientations showing pair of carbon atoms considered to measure diameter of C₄₀. The pair of carbon atoms chosen to calculate diameter in fig 9(a) are C₂₁ and C₃₇ having coordinates (-3.576, -0.173, -0.830) and (2.781, 0.320, 1.427) respectively which were substituted in distance formula to obtain the diameter of 6.76. Same follows for all other pair of carbon atoms shown in fig 9(b), 9(c), 9(d), 9(e). The average diameter obtained is 6.05Å.

Figure 9: Different orientations of C_{40} showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of diameter a) $C_{21}-C_{37}$, b) C_2-C_{34} , c) $C_{13}-C_{30}$, d) C_8-C_{18} , e) $C_{11}-C_{29}$.

Table 4: Diameters of C₄₀ corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen.

S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)	S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)
1	C ₂ -C ₃₄	6.76	6	C ₁₇ -C ₃₁	5.11
2	C ₁₁ -C ₂₉	6.11	7	C ₄ -C ₂₀	5.81
3	C ₁₃ -C ₃₀	5.07	8	C ₉ -C ₃₉	6.26
4	C ₁₈ -C ₈	5.19	9	C ₃₈ -C ₂₅	6.69
5	C ₂₁ -C ₃₇	6.76	10	C ₁ -C ₃₅	6.69

Different orientations of fullerene C₄₄ for measurement of diameter are shown in fig 10. The pair of carbon atoms chosen to measure the diameter in fig 10(a) are C₅ and C₄₂ having coordinates of (-3.917, 1.171, 0.381) and (4.203, -0.179, -0.645) respectively. These coordinates were substituted in distance formula to obtain the diameter of 8.28. Similarly fig 10(b), 10(c), 10(d) and 10(e) shows the pair of carbon atoms chosen to measure the diameters C₇-C₂₃, C₁₉-C₃₈, C₁₇-C₄₄ and C₂₆-C₃₆. The average diameter calculated is 6.64 Å.

Figure 10: Different orientations of C₄₄ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of diameter a) C₅-C₄₂ b) C₇-C₂₃ c) C₁₉-C₃₈ d) C₁₇-C₄₄ e) C₂₆-C₃₆.

Table 5: Diameters of C₄₄ corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen.

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)
1	C ₂₄ -C ₃₉	7.14	6	C ₁ -C ₄₃	8.30
2	C ₁₉ -C ₃₈	5.90	7	C ₂₅ -C ₃₇	4.53
3	C ₅ -C ₄₂	8.28	8	C ₂₆ -C ₃₆	5.20
4	C ₁₇ -C ₄₄	7.84	9	C ₂₇ -C ₃₄	6.79
5	C ₉ -C ₄₀	7.84	10	C ₃ -C ₂₂	4.62

Figure 11 shows different orientations of fullerene C₅₀ for measurement of diameters .the diameter corresponding to pair of carbon atoms chosen is C₉ and C₄₁ shown in fig 11(a). Their coordinates are (-1.415, 1.685, 1.134) and 1.435, -2.087, 0.017) which were substituted in distance formula to obtained the diameter of 4.85Å. Similarly fig 11(b), 11(c), 11(d) and 11(d) shows the pair of carbon atoms chosen to measure the diameter of C₃-C₃₀, C₃-C₂₂, C₆-C₄₉, C₁₁C₃₉.The average diameter calculated is 7.00 Å.

Figure 11: Different orientations of C₅₀ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of diameter a) C₉-C₄₁, b) C₃-C₃₀, c) C₃-C₂₂, d) C₆-C₄₉, e) C₁₁-C₃₉.

Table 6: Diameters of C_{50} corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen.

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter (in Å)
1	C13-C48	9.92	6	C1-C49	9.85
2	C3-C30	4.80	7	C25-C50	9.92
3	C11-C39	6.93	8	C16-C47	9.85
4	C9-C41	4.85	9	C27-C37	7.57
5	C7-C29	7.57	10	C5-C26	4.54

Figure 12 shows different orientations of fullerene C_{60} for measuring the diameter corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms. Atoms chosen in fig 11(a) are C_3 and C_{35} having coordinates (-1.01, 0.73, 3.36) and (1.01, -0.73, -3.36) which were substituted in distance formula to get the diameter of 7.16 Å as the diameter. Similarly fig 10(b), 10(c), 10(d), 10(e), shows the pair of carbon atoms chosen to measure the diameters C_{27} - C_{42} , C_{24} - C_{39} , C_{10} - C_{50} and C_{15} - C_{55} respectively. The average value calculated is 7.15 Å.

c)

d)

e)

Figure 12: Different orientations of C_{60} showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of diameter a) C_3-C_{35} , b) $C_{27}-C_{42}$, c) $C_{24}-C_{39}$, d) $C_{10}-C_{50}$, e) $C_{15}-C_{55}$.

Table 7: Diameters of C₆₀ corresponding to different pair of carbon atoms chosen.

S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Diameter in Å	S.NO	Possibilities	Diameter in Å
1	C ₂ -C ₃₄	7.16	6	C ₁ -C ₃₃	7.16
2	C ₃ -C ₃₅	7.16	7	C ₂₂ -C ₄₄	7.02
3	C ₁₅ -C ₅₅	7.17	8	C ₃₀ -C ₄₅	7.17
4	C ₂₄ -C ₃₉	7.16	9	C ₁₉ -C ₅₉	7.17
5	C ₂₇ -C ₄₂	7.16	10	C ₁₀ -C ₅₀	7.16

4.2 BOND LENGTH

The C-C single bond and C=C double bond lengths have been measured for C₂₈, C₃₂, C₃₆, C₄₀, C₄₄, C₅₀, C₆₀. The various orientations of a fullerene C₂₈ for bond length measurement are shown in fig.13 and the pair of carbon atoms involved for bond length measurement are C₂- C₃, C₄-C₅, C₂₅-C₂₇ in fig13(a) ; C₁₃-C₁₄, C₁₇-C₂₁, C₁₅-C₁₈ in fig.13(b) and C₁₃-C₁₄, C₁₇-C₂₁, C₁₆-C₂₂, C₉-C₁₂, C₂-C₃, C₁-C₂₀, C₁₅-C₁₈ in fig.13(c)

Figure 13: Different orientations of C₂₈ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of bond length.

Table 8 Calculated values of bond length for different pair of carbon atoms in C₂₈.

S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in (Å)	S.NO	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in (Å)
1	C ₂ -C ₃	1.43	7	C ₇ -C ₈	1.41
2	C ₄ -C ₅	1.51	8	C ₁ -C ₂₀	1.50
3	C ₁₅ -C ₁₈	1.47	9	C ₁₀ -C ₁₁	1.46
4	C ₁₇ -C ₂₁	1.52	10	C ₂₃ -C ₂₆	1.50
5	C ₂₅ -C ₂₇	1.53	11	C ₁₆ -C ₂₂	1.50
6	C ₁₃ -C ₁₄	1.42	12	C ₁₉ -C ₂₀	1.41

In case of C₃₂, figure 14 shows different orientations of C₃₂ for bond length measurement, the pair of carbon atoms involved in bond length measurement are C₁₀-C₂₃, C₁₃-C₁₉, C₂₂-C₂₆ in fig 14(a), C₂₁-C₂₅, C₂-C₇, C₁-C₄ in fig 14 (b) and C₁₃-C₁₄, C₁₇-C₂₁, C₉-C₁₂, C₁₅-C₁₈, C₂-C₃, C₁-C₂₀ in fig 14(c).

The bond lengths calculated for C₁-C₄, C₂-C₇, C₁₀-C₂₃, C₁₃-C₁₉, C₂₁-C₂₅, C₂₂-C₂₆, C₁₄-C₂₀, C₁₈-C₃₁, C₁₆-C₂₇, C₃-C₁₁, C₂₉-C₃₂ and C₉-C₁₅ are 1.45 Å, 1.45 Å, 1.40 Å, 1.51 Å, 1.49 Å, 1.49 Å, 1.50 Å, 1.44 Å, 1.44 Å, 1.44 Å, 1.46 Å and 1.50 Å respectively.

c)

Figure 14: Different orientations of C_{32} showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of bond length

Table 9: The calculated values of bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms in C_{32} .

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å
1	C ₁ -C ₄	1.45	7	C ₁₄ -C ₂₀	1.50
2	C ₂ -C ₇	1.45	8	C ₁₈ -C ₃₁	1.44
3	C ₁₀ -C ₂₃	1.40	9	C ₁₆ -C ₂₇	1.44
4	C ₁₃ -C ₁₉	1.51	10	C ₃ -C ₁₁	1.44
5	C ₂₁ -C ₂₅	1.49	11	C ₂₉ -C ₃₂	1.46
6	C ₂₂ -C ₂₆	1.49	12	C ₉ -C ₁₅	1.50

The various orientations of fullerene C₃₆ for bond length measurement are shown in **Figure 15** and the pair of carbon atoms involved in bond length measurement are C₉-C₃₃, C₁₅-C₁₈, C₃₁-C₃₂ in fig 15(a) C₂₃-C₂₇, C₆-C₂₀, C₁₁-C₁₄ in fig 15(b) and C₁₅-C₁₈, C₁₇-C₂₂, C₃₁-C₃₂, C₇-C₁₀, C₁₉-C₂₁, C₂₆-C₂₉, C₉-C₃₃.

Figure 15: Different orientations of C₃₆ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of bond length.

Table 10: Calculated values of bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms in C₃₆.

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å
1	C ₆ -C ₂₀	1.50	7	C ₁₉ -C ₂₁	1.45
2	C ₁₁ -C ₁₄	1.44	8	C ₂₂ -C ₂₆	1.49
3	C ₁₅ -C ₁₈	1.44	9	C ₂₄ -C ₂₅	1.45
4	C ₃₁ -C ₃₂	1.44	10	C ₃₄ -C ₃₅	1.49
5	C ₂₃ -C ₂₇	1.50	11	C ₅ -C ₈	1.42
6	C ₃₃ -C ₉	1.50	12	C ₇ -C ₁₀	1.42

The different orientations of fullerene C₄₀ for the bond length measurement are shown in Figure 16 and the pair of carbon atoms involved for bond length measurement are C₁₄-C₁₈, C₁₃-C₁₆, C₉-C₁₁ in fig 16(a), C₃₄-C₃₅, C₃₀-C₃₁ in fig 16(b) and C₄-C₅, C₇-C₈, C₂-C₃, C₂₆-C₂₈, C₁₃-C₁₆, C₁-C₂₅, C₃₉-C₄₀ in fig 16(c).

c)

Figure 16: Different orientations of C₄₀ showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of bond length.

Table 11: Calculated values of bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms in C₄₀.

S. No	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å	S. No	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å
1	C ₄ -C ₅	1.41	7	C ₂₃ -C ₃₃	1.47
2	C ₉ -C ₁₁	1.43	8	C ₃₉ -C ₄₀	1.42
3	C ₁₄ -C ₁₈	1.48	9	C ₃₆ -C ₃₇	1.43
4	C ₁₃ -C ₁₆	1.41	10	C ₃ -C ₁₂	1.46
5	C ₃₀ -C ₃₁	1.48	11	C ₂₂ -C ₃₂	1.47
6	C ₃₄ -C ₃₅	1.42	12	C ₁₇ -C ₃₆	1.46

Figure 17 shows different orientations of fullerene C_{44} for measurement of bond lengths and the pair of carbon atoms involved are C_{35} - C_{36} , C_{24} - C_{29} , C_2 - C_{34} in fig 17(a); C_1 - C_{17} , C_9 - C_{16} , C_3 - C_8 , C_{24} - C_{29} , C_{11} - C_{27} in fig 17(b) and C_2 - C_{34} , C_{24} - C_{29} , C_{35} - C_{36} , C_1 - C_{17} , C_{12} - C_{25} , C_{40} - C_{42} in fig 17(c).

Figure 17: Different orientations of C_{44} showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of bond length.

Table 12 Calculated values of bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms in C₄₄.

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in (Å)	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in (Å)
1	C ₃₅ -C ₃₆	1.47	8	C ₃ -C ₈	1.46
2	C ₄ -C ₄₂	1.50	9	C ₁ -C ₁₇	1.50
3	C ₁₂ -C ₂₅	1.48	10	C ₂₀ -C ₃₀	1.49
4	C ₉ -C ₁₆	1.481	11	C ₂ -C ₃₄	1.41
5	C ₂₄ -C ₂₉	1.47	12	C ₃ -C ₄	1.45
6	C ₂₂ -C ₂₃	1.47	13	C ₃₁ -C ₃₂	1.43
7	C ₁₁ -C ₂₇	1.45	14	C ₇ -C ₁₅	1.44

The different orientations of fullerene C₅₀ for the bond length measurement are shown **Figure 18** and the pair of carbon atoms involved for bond length measurement are C₂₆-C₃₁, C₄₀-C₄₁, C₁₆-C₁₉ in fig 18(a) C₁₄-C₂₃, C₁-C₂, C₄₆-C₅₀ in fig 18(b) and C₂₂-C₃₂, C₁₆-C₁₉, C₁₅-C₁₈, C₁₄-C₂₃, C₅-C₈, C₃₃-C₄₉, C₁₁-C₁₂, C₄₀-C₄₁ in fig 18(c).

c)

Figure 18: Different orientations of C_{50} showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of bond length.

Table 13. Calculated values of bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms in C_{50} .

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length (in Å)	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length (in Å)
1	C ₁₆ -C ₁₉	1.46	8	C ₁ -C ₂	1.43
2	C ₂₆ -C ₃₁	1.46	9	C ₁₄ -C ₂₃	1.42
3	C ₅₀ -C ₄₆	1.47	10	C ₄₃ -C ₄₇	1.43
4	C ₁₅ -C ₁₈	1.48	11	C ₄₅ -C ₄₈	1.42
5	C ₅ -C ₁₂	1.46	12	C ₂₉ -C ₃₀	1.43
6	C ₃₃ -C ₄₉	1.46	13	C ₂₂ -C ₃₂	1.42
7	C ₃ -C ₃₄	1.49	14	C ₁₁ -C ₁₂	1.43

Different orientations of fullerene C_{60} for the measurement of bond length are shown in fig 19 and the pair of carbon atoms involved for bond length measurement are C_{10} - C_{56} , C_{15} - C_{36} , C_1 - C_2 , C_{16} - C_{20} in fig 19(a), C_{35} - C_{58} , C_{21} - C_{22} in fig 19(b) and C_1 - C_2 , C_{17} - C_{24} , C_{11} - C_{45} , C_{21} - C_{22} , C_{16} - C_{20} .

Figure 19: Different orientations of C_{60} showing the pair of carbon atoms involved in the measurement of bond length.

Table 14 Calculated values of bond lengths for different pair of carbon atoms in C₆₀. All the pair of carbon atoms having value 1.46 Å show single bonds and all the pair of carbon atoms having value 1.41 Å shows double bonds. C₆₀ has two bond lengths and the average bond length is 1.4 Å.

S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å	S.NO.	Pair of carbon atoms	Bond length in Å
1	C ₁ -C ₂	1.46	8	C ₁₀ -C ₅₆	1.41
2	C ₁₆ -C ₂₀	1.46	9	C ₁₅ -C ₃₆	1.41
3	C ₂₁ -C ₂₂	1.46	10	C ₃₅ -C ₅₈	1.41
4	C ₄₂ -C ₄₃	1.46	11	C ₁₁ -C ₄₅	1.41
5	C ₄₇ -C ₄₈	1.46	12	C ₅ -C ₂₈	1.41
6	C ₅₁ -C ₅₂	1.46	13	C ₁₇ -C ₂₄	1.41
7	C ₂₆ -C ₂₇	1.46	14	C ₃₄ -C ₅₃	1.41

Table 15 shows the average diameters and bond lengths for all the fullerenes considered in this work. The average diameter is minimum (4.89) Å for C₂₈ and maximum (7.15) Å for C₆₀ which is in agreement with experimental value reported in the literature as (7.14) Å [43]. It can be concluded that the value of single bond lengths are greater than the value of double bond lengths.

TABLE 15: shows the average diameter and range of single and double bond length in different fullerenes.

S.NO	Fullerenes	Average diameter (in Å)	Bond length (in Å)	
			C-C	C=C
1	C ₂₈	4.89	1.50-1.53	1.41-1.47
2	C ₃₂	5.19	1.46-1.51	1.40-1.45
3	C ₃₆	5.52	1.46-1.50	1.42-1.45
4	C ₄₀	6.05	1.45-1.48	1.41-1.44
5	C ₄₄	6.64	1.46-1.50	1.41-1.45
6	C ₅₀	7.00	1.46-1.48	1.42-1.45
7	C ₆₀	7.15	1.46	1.41

Figure 20: Average diameters of fullerenes

4.3 SURFACE CURVATURE

The Surface Curvature of fullerenes have been calculated in the terms of pyramidalization angle using POAV circular cone model formulas. To calculate the Pyramidalization angle choose one central atom and three neighborhood atoms in the fullerene. Central atom considered as 'O' and neighborhood three atoms considered as A,B,C respectively. Then find out the Central atom and neighborhood atoms coordinates from VESTA and put these coordinates value in the POAV method equations. It gives the pyramidalization angle value that shows the surface curvature of the fullerene.

Calculation of Pyramidalization Angle in C₂₈

To study the surface curvature in C₂₈ fullerene pyramidalization angle is calculated at different sites on the surface of fullerene. In figure 21(a) the central atom is C₁₄ and the surrounding atoms as C₂₀, C₁₃ and C₁₇ at this site. Similarly, in figure 21(b) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₁₀ and the surrounding atom are C₁₁, C₁₈ and C₉ and similarly in figure 21(c) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₂₇ and the surrounding atoms are C₂₈, C₂₂ and C₂₅.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 21: Calculation of pyramidalization angle at the site of carbon atom (a) C₁₄, (b) C₁₀, (c) C₂₇ in fullerene C₂₈.

Calculation of Pyramidalization Angle in C₃₂

To study the surface curvature in C₃₂ fullerene pyramidalization angle is calculated at different sites on the surface of fullerene. In figure 22(a) the central atom is C₄ and the surrounding atoms as C₁₇, C₉ and C₁ at this site. Similarly, in figure 22(b) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₁₃ and the surrounding atom are C₁₉, C₂₄ and C₆ and similarly in figure 22(c) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₂₈ and the surrounding atoms are C₁₇, C₃₁ and C₂₅.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 22: Calculation of pyramidalization angle at the site of carbon atom (a) C₄, (b) C₁₃, (c) C₂₈ in fullerene C₃₂.

Calculation of Pyramidalization Angle in C₃₆

To study the surface curvature in C₃₆ fullerene pyramidalization angle is calculated at different sites on the surface of fullerene. In figure 23(a) the central atom is C₉ and the surrounding atoms as C₁₀, C₃₃ and C₈ at this site. Similarly, in figure 23(b) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₁ and the surrounding atom are C₁, C₂₅ and C₄ and similarly in figure 23(c) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₂ and the surrounding atoms are C₂₈, C₃ and C₂₄.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 23: Calculation of pyramidalization angle at the site of carbon atom (a) C₉, (b) C₁, (c) C₂ in fullerene C₃₆.

Calculation of Pyramidalization Angle in C₄₀

To study the surface curvature in C₄₀ fullerene pyramidalization angle is calculated at different sites on the surface of fullerene. In figure 24(a) the central atom is C₃₆ and the surrounding atoms as C₈, C₁₇ and C₃₇ at this site. Similarly, in figure 24(b) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₆ and the surrounding atom are C₁₇, C₃ and C₅ and similarly in figure 24(c) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₁₇ and the surrounding atoms are C₃₆, C₆ and C₁₃.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 24: Calculation of pyramidalization angle at the site of carbon atom (a) C₃₆, (b) C₆, (c) C₁₇ in fullerene C₄₀.

Calculation of Pyramidalization Angle in C₄₄

To study the surface curvature in C₄₄ fullerene pyramidalization angle is calculated at different sites on the surface of fullerene. In figure 25(a) the central atom is C₃₈ and the surrounding atoms as C₄₁, C₇ and C₄₁ at this site. Similarly, in figure 25(b) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₆ and the surrounding atom are C₁₇, C₃ and C₅ and similarly in figure 25(c) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₈ and the surrounding atoms are C₇, C₃ and C₁₃.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 25: Calculation of pyramidalization angle at the site of carbon atom (a) C₃₈, (b) C₁, (c) C₈ in fullerene C₄₄.

Calculation of Pyramidalization Angle in C₅₀

To study the surface curvature in C₅₀ fullerene pyramidalization angle is calculated at different sites on the surface of fullerene. In figure 26(a) the central atom is C₄ and the surrounding atoms as C₃, C₂ and C₇ at this site. Similarly, in figure 26(b) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₇ and the surrounding atom are C₁₀, C₆ and C₄ and similarly in figure 26(c) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₈ and the surrounding atoms are C₇, C₃ and C₁₃.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 26: Calculation of pyramidalization angle at the site of carbon atom (a) C₄, (b) C₇, (c) C₈ in fullerene C₅₀.

Calculation of Pyramidalization Angle in C₆₀

To study the surface curvature in C₆₀ fullerene pyramidalization angle is calculated at different sites on the surface of fullerene. In figure 27(a) the central atom is C₄ and the surrounding atoms as C₃, C₂ and C₇ at this site. Similarly, in figure 27(b) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₇ and the surrounding atom are C₁₀, C₆ and C₄ and similarly in figure 27(c) the site has been changed as the central atom is C₈ and the surrounding atoms are C₇, C₃ and C₁₃.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 27: Calculation of pyramidalization angle at the site of carbon atom (a) C₄₆, (b) C₄, (c) C₁₈ in fullerene C₆₀.

S.No.	Fullerenes	Pyramidalization Angle (in degree)	
		Calculated Value	Reported Value
1	C ₂₈	17.43	17.58
		16.60	17.58
		19.80	18.83
2	C ₃₂	17.28	17.50
		17.21	17.50
		13.99	14.36
3	C ₃₆	17.03	17.11
		15.98	16.00
		15.98	16.00
4	C ₄₀	12.18	11.3
		13.91	14.52
		15.68	16.06
5	C ₄₄	13.26	13.18
		19.01	18.00
		10.12	12.14
6	C ₅₀	11.96	12.46
		16.28	15.50

		09.08	10.72
7	C ₆₀	11.45	11.64
		11.56	11.64
		11.77	11.64

Table 22: Calculated values of pyramidalization angle for different pair of carbon atoms in various kind of fullerenes such as C₂₈, C₃₂, C₃₆, C₄₀, C₄₄, C₅₀ and C₆₀ Meanwhile here taken the reported value of pyramidalization angle from the literature[50].

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE OF WORK

CONCLUSION

In the present work, ground state structure of pure fullerenes to study the structural properties. The average diameters of different fullerenes were calculated and were found to increase with increase in size of fullerene. The average diameter is found to be minimum 4.89 Å for C₂₈ while it is maximum 7.15 Å for C₆₀. Also the measured values of bond lengths have been classified into 2 categories namely C-C and C=C. The results also conclude that C=C bond length is smaller than C-C bond length in all the fullerenes considered. The pyramidalization angle in fullerenes taking into account the different sites on the surface. In C₂₈, C₃₂, C₃₆, C₄₀, C₄₄, C₅₀ and C₆₀ fullerenes the pyramidalization angle varies from 17.43' to 19.80', 13.99' to 17.28', 15.98' to 17.03', 12.18' to 15.68', 10.12' to 19.01', 09.08' to 16.28' and 11.45' to 11.77'. The results are in agreement with the reported values in the literature.

It has been observed that the pyramidalization angle tends to decrease with increase in size of fullerenes. The value of pyramidalization angle reflects the surface curvature of fullerenes and subsequently the reactivity.

FUTURE SCOPE OF WORK

The discovery of these molecules has been the foundation of research in many interdisciplinary fields like Nanoscience, Pharmaceuticals, Electronics, Technology etc. The pyramidalization angle is related to the surface curvature of fullerenes. The surface curvature further describes the reactivity of a particular nanostructure. Thus, these fullerenes may be used to carry out dehydrogenation of complex metal hydrides. Further, one or more substitutional Boron (B) doping may be performed to enhance the dehydrogenation behavior. The versatility of the fullerene molecules in a way that their physical and chemical properties such as their capacity to form endohedral, exohedral derivatives, electron accepting nature, mechanical strength, negligible bio toxicity of these Nano forms of carbon has paved the way for their long run in near future. Fullerenes hold great promise in the health care industry especially in Pharmaceuticals. This has resulted in an increased no of research work in recent years making it a hot topic. Here, we focus on some applications in which fullerenes can be made use of:

Antioxidants and biopharmaceuticals

Since fullerenes react easily with free radicals, which are harmful for our body, fullerenes could act as antioxidants. Much research work has been carried out in the control of nervous damage caused due to Alzheimer's and Lou Gehrig's disease. The sponge like effect of fullerenes towards radicals, results in destruction of 20 free radicals per C₆₀ radical. The bioactivity of fullerene based antioxidants is 100 times more effective than the current leading drugs in the market.

Drug delivery

Attachment of hydrophilic moieties to the hydrophobic C₆₀ fullerene makes its soluble in water. As a result they become capable of transporting drugs to the cells. These functionalized fullerenes can cross the cell membrane and bind with the mitochondria. DNA functionalized fullerenes show better efficiency as compared to available lipid based vectors, by providing a protective sheath around the DNA, thus increasing its lifetime in endosomes.

Microelectronics

IMEC and NANTERO are developing a memory chip that uses carbon nanotubes. This memory is labeled NRAM for nanotube based non volatile random access memory and is intended to be used in place of high density flash memory chips.

Defense

The Institute of soldier nanotechnologies are in the business of taking help from nanotechnology to help soldiers survive in battle conditions. A nanobattle suit is being developed that could be as thin as spandex and contain health monitors and communication equipments. Nanoparticles also provide strength that surpasses currently available material, providing bullet shielding that's more effective. These jumpsuit style outfits might even be able to react to and stop biological and chemical attacks.

Hydrogen storage in automobiles

Storing hydrogen for fuel cell powered cars. Using graphene layers to increase the binding energy of hydrogen to the graphene surface in a fuel tank, results in a higher amount of hydrogen storage and a lighter weight fuel tank. This could help in the development of practical hydrogen fueled cars.

Increasing the electricity generated by windmills

Epoxy containing carbon nanotubes is being used to make windmill blades. The resulting blades are stronger and less in weight, therefore the amount of electricity generated by each windmill is greater.

CHAPTER 6

REFERENCES

1. H W Kroto, A W Allaf and S P Balm, C₆₀: Buckminsterfullerene, Chemical Reviews, Vol.91, No.6, pp.1213–1235, **1991**.
2. Kratschmer, W., Lamb, L.D. and Hoffman, D.R., Nature, **1990**, 347, 354.
3. Morgan, G. J., **2003** “Historical Review: Viruses, Crystals and Geodesic Domes”. Trends in Bio chemical science 28, pp. 86-90.
4. H W Kroto, A W Allaf and S P Balm, C 60: Buckminsterfullerene, Chemical Reviews, Vol.91, No.6, pp.1213–1235, **1991**.
5. Morgan, G. J., 2003 “Historical Review: Viruses, Crystals and Geodesic Domes”. Trends in Bio chemical science 28, pp. 86-90.
6. Iijima S. Direct Observation of the Tetrahedral Bonding in Graphitized Carbon Black by High Resolution Electron Microscopy. J Cryst Growth. **1980**; 50(3): 675–683p.
7. Iijima S. Direct Observation of the Tetrahedral Bonding in Graphitized Carbon Black by High Resolution Electron Microscopy. J Cryst Growth. **1980**; 50(3): 675–683p.
8. Buseck PR, Tsipursky SJ, Hettich R. Fullerenes from the Geological Environment. Science. **1992**; 257(5067): 215–7p.
9. Iijima Sumio. Helical Microtubules of Graphitic Carbon. Nature. **1991**; 354: 56– 58p
10. Atkinson Nancy. Buckyballs Could Be Plentiful in the Universe. Universe Today. **2010**.
11. Mitchel DR, Brown R, Malcolm Jr. The Synthesis of Megatubes: New Dimensions in Carbon Materials. Inorg Chem. **2001**; 40(12): 2751–5p.
12. Shvartsburg AA, Hudgins RR, Gutierrez Rafael, et al. Ball-and-Chain Dimers from a Hot Fullerene Plasma (PDF). J Phys Chem A. **1999**; 103(27): 5275–5284p.
13. Sano N, Wang H, Chhowalla M, et al. Synthesis of Carbon 'Onions' in Water. Nature. **2001**; 414(6863): 506–7p.
14. Kroto HW, Heath JR, O'Brien SC, et al. C₆₀: Buckminsterfullerene. Nature. **1985**; 318(6042): 162–163p.
15. K E Geckeler and S Samal, Syntheses and properties of macro molecular fullerenes, a review, Polymer International, Volo.48, No.9, pp.743– 757, **1999**.
16. Qiao, W.; Li, X.; Bai, H.; Zhu, Y.; Huang, Y. Structure and electronic properties of the nanopeapods-one dimensional C₆₀O polymer encapsulated in single-walled carbon nanotubes. *J. Solid State Chem.* **2012**, 186, 64–69.

17. Bai, H.; Ai, Y.; Huang, Y. Theoretical studies of one-dimensional C₃₆ coplanar polymers. *Phys. Status Solidi B* **2011**, 248, 969–973.
18. Bai, H.; Du, R.; Qiao, W.; Huang, Y. Structures, stabilities and electronic properties of C₅₀ dimers. *J. Mol. Struct.: Theochem.* **2010**, 961, 42–47.
19. Chen, L.; Chen, Y.; Xiao, H.; Li, H.; Li, J. Addition reaction of Fe(CO)_n (*n* = 3–5) on fullerene C₅₀, C₆₀, and C₇₀: A density functional theory study. *Chin. J. Struct. Chem.* **2011**, 30, 1161-1167.
20. Jia, G.; Liu, L.; Qiao, X.; Zhang, Y.; Li, J. Prediction of the frontier electronic states in a finite single-wall carbon nanotube. *Chin. J. Struct. Chem.* **2012**, 31, 223–234.
21. Xu, X.; Shang Z.; Li, R.; Cai, Z.; Zhao, X. Comparative theoretical study of methano- and imino-[50] fullerenes: C₅₀CH₂ and C₅₀NH. *J. Mol. Struct.: Theochem.* **2006**, 760, 99-107.
22. Moradi, O.; Yari, M.; Zare, K.; Mirza, B.; Najafi, F. Carbon nanotubes: A review of chemistry principles and reactions. *Fullerenes, Nanotubes and Carbon Nanostructures* **2012**, 20, 138-151.
23. Bai, H.; Qiao, W.; Zhu, Y.; Huang, Y. Theoretical study on one-dimensional C₅₀ polymers. *Diamond Relat. Mater.* **2012**, 26, 20–24.
24. Warner, J. H.; Schaffel, F.; Zhong, G.; Rummeli, M. H.; Buchner, B.; Robertson, J.; Briggs, G. A. D. Investigating the diameter-dependent stability of single-walled carbon nanotubes. *ACS Nano.* **2009**, 3, 1557–1563.
25. Zhang, W.; Sprafke, J. K.; Ma, M.; Tsui, E. Y.; Sydlik, S. A.; Rutledge, G. C.; Swager, T. M. Modular functionalization of carbon nanotubes and fullerenes. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, 131, 8446-8454.
26. Haddon, R. C.; Scott, L. T. π -orbital conjugation and rehybridization in bridged annulenes and deformed molecules in general: π -orbital axis vector analysis. *Pure Appl. Chem.* **1986**, 58, 137–1426.
27. Song, X.; Liu, S.; Yan, H.; Gan, Z. First-principles study on effects of mechanical deformation on outer surface reactivity of carbon nanotubes. *Physica E* **2009**, 41, 626–630.
28. Haddon, R. C. Comment on the relationship of the pyramidalization angle at a conjugated carbon atom to the σ bond angles. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2001**, 105, 4164-4165.
29. Lu, X.; Chen, Z. Curved pi-conjugation, aromaticity, and the related chemistry of small fullerenes (<C₆₀) and single-walled carbon nanotubes. *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, 105, 3643–3696.
30. Niyogi, S.; Hamon, M. A.; Hu, H.; Zhao, B.; Bhowmik, P.; Sen, R.; Itkis, M. E.; Haddon, R. C. Chemistry of single-walled carbon nanotubes. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2002**, 35, 1105–1113.

31. Haddon, R. C. Chemistry of the fullerenes: the manifestation of strain in a class of continuous aromatic molecules. *Science* **1993**, 261, 1545–1550.
32. Smalley, R. E. Self-assembly of the fullerenes. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **25**, 98–105 (1992).
33. Goroff, N. S. Mechanism of fullerene formation. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **29**, 77–83 (1996).
34. Heath, J. R. Synthesis of C₆₀ from small carbon clusters: a model based on experiment and theory. *ACS Symp. Ser.* **481**, 1–23 (1991).
35. Hunter, J. M., Fye, J. F., Roskamp, E. J. & Jarrold, M. F. Annealing carbon cluster ions—a mechanism for fullerene synthesis. *J. Phys. Chem.* **98**, 1810–1818 (1992).
36. Rubin, Y., Kahr, M., Knobler, C. B., Diederich, F. & Wilkins, C. L. The higher oxides of carbon C_{8n}O_{2n} (n^{1/3}–5): synthesis, characterization and X-ray crystal structure. Formation of cyclo[n]carbon ions C_n⁺ (n^{1/18}, 24), C_n²⁺ (n^{1/18}, 24, 30), and higher carbon ions including C₆₀⁺ in laser desorption Fourier transform mass spectrometric experiments. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **113**, 495–500 (1991).
37. Irlé, S., Zheng, G., Wang, Z. & Morokuma, K. The C₆₀ formation puzzle ‘solved’: QM/MD simulations reveal the shrinking hot giant road of the dynamic fullerene self-assembly mechanism. *J. Chem. Phys. B* **110**, 14531–14545 (2006).
38. Huang, J. Y., Ding, F., Jiao, K. & Yakobson, B. I. Real time microscopy, kinetics and mechanism of giant fullerene evaporation. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **99**, 175503 (2007).
39. Lozovik, Y. E. & Popov, A. M. Formation and growth of carbon nanostructures: fullerenes, nanoparticles, nanotubes and cones. *Uspekhi Fizicheskikh Nauk* **167**, 751–774 (1997).
40. Eggen, B. R. et al. Autocatalysis during fullerene growth. *Science* **272**, 87–90 (1996).
41. Kroto, H. W.; McKay, K. *Nature* **1988**, 331, 328–331. Kroto, H. W. *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.* **1990**, **86**, 2465–2468.
42. (Xie et al. **2004**, Wang et al. **2006**).
43. N. Kurita, N. Koboyashi, H. Kumabara, and K. Tago, *Phys. Rev. B* **48**, 4850 (1993).
44. Okada, S.; Oshiyama, A. Curvature-induced metallization of double-walled semiconducting zigzag carbon nanotubes. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **2003**, **91**, 21680(1–4).
45. Bai, H.; Qiao, W.; Wang, G.; Huang, Y. Theoretical study on the peanut-shaped dimers and nanotubes consisted of C₅₀ cages. *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.* **2011**, **11**, 11104–11108.
46. Haddon, R. C. π -electrons in three dimensions. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **1988**, **21**, 243–249.
47. Carrazana-García, J. A.; Rodríguez-Otero, J.; Cabaleiro-Lago, E. M. DFT study of the interaction between alkaline cations and molecular bowls derived from fullerene. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2011**, **115**, 2774–2782.

48. Dinadayalane, T. C.; Afanasiev, D.; Leszczynski, J. Structures and energetics of the cation- π interactions of Li^+ , Na^+ , and K^+ with cup-shaped molecules: effect of ring addition to benzene and cavity selectivity. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2008**, 112, 7916-7924.
49. Haddon, R. C.; Chow, S. Hybridization as a metric for the reaction coordinate of the chemical reaction. Concert in chemical reactions. . *Pure Appl. Chem.* **1999**, 71, 289-294.
50. BAI Hong-Cun, ZHU Ying, YUAN Ni-Ni, New Solution Method of π -Orbital Axis Vector and Its Applications in Fullerenes and Carbon Nanotubes. *Chinese J. Struct. Chem.* **2013**, 32, 695-703.